

Strategic Role of Human Resource Management Policies and Practices in Organizational Change

*Saqlain Sher, Ulfat Abbas, Rao Arif Mahmood Khan, Nasreen Khan, Hanzla Ahmed, Hafiz Muhammad Ammar Zafar

1, 2, 3, 5, 6 *Institute of Business Management & Administrative Sciences, The Islamia University Bahawalpur (PAK)*

4 *Faculty of Management Sciences, SZABIST Dubai Campus (UAE)*

* Corresponding author email: saqlainsher@hotmail.com

Received: 07th July 2021

Revised: 21st August 2021

Accepted: 03rd September 2021

Abstract: This research study mainly answers the relationship between HR practices and strategies with organizational change, the vital role of HR towards effective change in any organization, and core HR policies and practices critical for significant organizational change. There is no way to avoid change in the present world of competitive environments and to thrive in the current era's economy. The researcher has studied the approach of HRM in the XYZ organization. The organization has implemented various changes (small too big). During those change processes, what role HRM has played in ensuring that the people and HRM policies and practices align with the proposed changes, and HR facilitates the change to make it efficient. An organization cannot operate and build towards an efficient workforce without proficient Human Resource Management (HRM). HR Professionals' proactive participation in managing people issues resulting from change is a significant distinguisher success factor in the change process. This study has explained various external and internal factors in organizational change, external factors like Policies of Government, Social Pressure, Raw Material Cost, Technology, and Internal Factors like Profit Declination, Change Leadership, and Action of Union.

Keywords: HR Practices, HR Strategies, Organizational Change, Communication, Culture, Competition, Role of HR in Change.

1. Introduction

Change management is needed as it provides opportunities to the organizations to bring the desired changes like sustainability, profit, expansion, growth, or any other required favorable outcome. Therefore they are seen to be facilitating the employees to provide positive changes in the organization. HR has an

essential role in the development of an organization, and thus it supports bringing positive changes in the organization. The different HR practices can quickly resolve employees who are seen to be coping with the changes likely. HR can positively change the employees' behavior from negative to positive, from resistant to supporting.

In pursuit of the desired outcomes, HR department should be encouraged to search for the people who could facilitate the change process as it could motivate the employees to take part in the change initiatives. They are the change agents and have crucial role to change the face of the organization. For this HR department is usually provided with the staff who have the relevant knowledge related to the people's behavior, providing them with the experience about the importance of change and considering the change management as the most crucial strategy of the HR (Tummers et al. 2013). Different big companies are supported by the HR managers that allow them to change positively as the various change initiatives provide the employees with the rewards. In the future, they are provided with the proper support for taking the initiatives for the change. In the current global competitive environment, organizational change is not avoidable, and this change transfers the organization's present situation towards the desired position. Every organization willing for change has to pass through a transition phase through its HR department. It plays a vital role in building very much confidence and creating a stable environment whenever the organization wants to change. Now the question arises when change occurs? Change in an organization is occurs when a crisis arises; gaps exist in performance, new technology's arrives, through the rectification of opportunities, acquisitions, mergers, and reaction towards internal and external pressure. The HR department plays a fundamental guidance role in helping and coordinate the execution of the business plan through its strategic moves. HR practices give an active and supporting foundation towards its capital for its betterment in the short and long term. With the backing of Human Resource Management practices and the sound basis of management, every organization can heighten group innovation (Tan & Nasurdin, 2011).

On the other hand, HR strategies are the plan that leads to a change in specific Human Resource functional areas. These policies facilitate management decisions that ensure the most suitable option for the betterment of the organization. Many companies are implementing a change in an organization's workplace because they want to stay in business among their rivals (Iveta, 2012).

Presently, most organizations are much greater in number or influence dynamically concerning affectations through many opportunities and various day-to-day challenges for policymakers and organization practitioners (Adewale & Antbonia, 2013). Organizations need to be adaptable to the changing environment, and thus change becomes constant. Change cannot be implemented unless employees are involved in the change and accepting the change. Their willingness and readiness for change is a critical factor for successful change management. High-Performance work practices help organizations to engage employees in the change process and facilitate the change. (Boselie et al., 2005). HRM practices need to be aligned with organizational change processes. As mentioned by the researcher, based upon the way change has been managed in XYZ Engineering and the role HR has played in ensuring effective change management, this case study based research has been undertaken. As understood, every organization change and that may be a major or some minor modification. However, unless the change is managed correctly and employee participation is encouraged, success cannot be achieved.

This research study mainly answers the relationship between HR practices and strategies with organizational change, the vital role of HR towards effective change in any organization, and core HR policies and procedures critical for effective organizational change. This research study provides a clear picture regarding HR Practices and Strategies in implementing change within the workplace of any organization of the United Arab Emirates and the globe.

Change is inevitable in any organization for growth, sustainment, and profit in the present world of the competitive environment, but adapting to change is painful. Organizational change can cause much anxiety, fear, demotivation, and low morale in employees, which are the primary causes of resistance for a change in an organization. There is no way to avoid change; it is transforming the current situation towards the desired situation. Every organization takes a step and a quick change pace to stick in a competitive and challenging environment. For organizational change within an organization's workplace, they use HRM's change strategies and practices to improve their vision, mission, the introduction of new technologies, and enhance performance or introduce a new policy. One of the change process's core elements is linking the gap between the strategic practice and aim and its people.

An organization cannot operate and build towards an efficient workforce without proficient Human Resource Management (HRM). There are multiple core functions performed by HRM. They are motivating to employees, effective workplace communication, recruitment of workforce, an arrangement of a training session, performance management systems, providing a safe, positive work environment, employee engagement, and, most notably, the proper use of HR practices and its strategies in implementing change in an organization. Creating a positive work environment is one of HRM's core functions, which may be achieved by establishing consistent, transparent, and clear policies in any organization, the rule of law, employee feedback, and trust among employees and employers. Another critical responsibility of the HR Department is managing employee conflict, which may be an interpersonal, task, or cultural conflict; it can be a significant contributor to the failure of any change in an organization. In the current competitive world, frequent change is essential, but their employees become frightened due to a change in structure. There are different reactions, which are depression, anger, opposition, and denial. Resistance behaviors can vary from individual to others; such employee productivity will be relatively much low. Managers may be curious to deal with such employees directly, rather than tackling significant reasons for resistance to change; managers must deal with the source of those symptoms. HR Managers can help managers understand the emotions and thoughts that come with the organization's change, identify the possible causes of employee resistance, and then use persuasive techniques to define and resolve those root causes for resistance. HRM team can also help employee managers discuss the underlying merits of change within an organization's workplace, supporting this current and exciting attitude. After that, there is a need to describe how to complete change will bring, how organization shifts from existing states to new states, the main opportunities we can avail after implementing this change within the organization's workplace, and much more.

Therefore, the literature reviews of some essential research journals are elaborated. Muchira & Kiambati (2015) have explained the Human Resource Department (HRD) regarding change agents. In this research, they point out that there is a need to focus on change frequently for maintaining any business in the current competitive marketplace. Change support to enhance and improve the level of productivity, which

increases the sales of an organization. The development of worldwide competition and advancements in unique technology anticipates a going forward demand for change. They further narrate that the organization will require various services regarding change agent for assisting in their effort to implement change successfully. In this research journal, they identify the critical role of HRD regarding change agents within several areas like management of organizational change, various roles which played through the management of change, different competencies, and skills for Human Resource Development change agents. In this research study, the three steps study model of Lawin and eight steps of Kotter used. Finally, this research study sums up with suggestions for future research.

Chew, Cheng, & Lazarevic (2006) narrates regarding a manager's role in carrying out organizational change by taking the restaurant industry case in Melbourne. This research journal elaborates that the restaurant industry is a core hospitality sector that is very responsive to physical and external environment changes. If restaurants want to stay in the current market competition, they need to be flexible for quick reactions, and they need to assume every change occurring in the external environment. Close relationships and interactions among managers and employees ultimately affect restaurants' performance whenever external and internal changes occur. The research study was carried out in Melbourne City because this city has excellent dining styles. This research study focused on the manager's role whenever starting and enforcing organizational change to minimize employees' resistance during the change process. The main finding of this research journal helps several previous theoretical techniques to efficient change management. Finally, this research study found that the core aspects that support change our employees' attitude, effective communication, and manager's perception and actions.

Liu (2009) narrates regarding organizational change approaches. He explains that organizational change is an adrift for developments in the future, and this aspect gives way to the quest for scholars in various numbers of fields. In this research journal, two core kinds of models have been used for organizational change: a new and prescriptive approach. In this research, further Peter's Seven S Framework and his colleague demonstrate interrelationships among various corporate practices and strategy aspects. This study focused on looking for a company's current trends for enforcing their change management with general directions. A single approach cannot fulfill the entire company's requirements. Finally, this research's key finding was regarding organization learning ability during various and incremental change strategies; it is one of the best and efficient directions to keep an organization's competitive ability along with a noisy environment.

Sani (2012) explains regarding organizational performance and strategic HRM insurance industry of Nigeria. In this research, the journal explores various strategic HRM practices and techniques on organizational performance. Examining the strength of strategic HRM techniques and procedures on an organization's performance depends on its workplace environment. A survey was applied to 18 insurance companies, data collected through this survey, and then correlation and regression analysis. The tool used for the measurement of organizational climate was a questionnaire that they build with the help of various eight climate dimensions of an organization. This research clearly shows that the strategic HRM alignment, job definition, line management training, and career planning system are core strategic HR practices that determine an organization's performance in Nigeria's insurance industry. This research journal reveals the

relationship between organizational performance & strategic practices of HR through the corporate environment.

Burma (2014) describes the importance of Human Resource Management in present-day organizations. This research study explains that the core element is global competition towards organizational practices and strategies in the current world. Due to this, every industrial economy passes through experiences toward the right knowledge economy. Before this, a mostly organization just focuses on its total quality; efficiency only is accomplished through proper human resources utilization. HRM is fundamental for modern competitive business. HRM's department has a significant action towards the supply of human capital towards firms' core resources. HRM's department has a crucial role in the recruitments of personnel, performance appraisal, and orientation. This research study investigates how HR issues can address effective strategic decisions from organizational management. This research study will communicate the importance of HRM, affecting factors, and the HRM functions of HRM, and the relationship between HRM & organizational effectiveness.

Latta (2009) narrates the organizational change process model towards cultural context; his focus was on corporate culture's impact on change. Every change occupies the leadership heart. An organization's culture is one of the core position variables that came out regarding polar in finding its success and efforts towards implementing change with the first step. In this journal, the organizational change process model discussed in the cultural context is deduced from an ethnographic analysis. This model defines the secondary effect of corporate culture on each level of organizational change implementation. In this research study, influences of culture along eight stages are rectified and exemplified. There are several suggestions stated for enhancement elaboration along with this model.

The main findings of this research study were the exploration of practical and theoretical implications for leadership. Finally, it is discussed solving organizational issues through organizational change.

According to Alas, Allikmae, & Varts (2012), change is perceived as an essential element for survival when it comes to uncertainty. The organizational change is the change that is seen when the different individuals are agreed to change their attitude and behavior. The various changes in the global environment have contributed to issues that are highly complex and could lead to unpredictable scenarios. Due to this shift, it is seen that focus is shifted to bringing the change and the different attitudes related to the change so that the different organizations can make the innovation in the product. The various changes demand the organizations to bring changes to cope with the different issues. The research related to the organizational change is divided into contextual research, content research, criterion research, and process research. Nutt (2003) has combined the two things; together, including the process and the structure.

The concept of human resource management is seen to be getting importance as it is becoming more evident to the different companies that how vital the strategies are for the organization. It is considered that due to the potential impact of these strategies, organizations are perceived to be paying attention to strategic management (Tummers et al., 2013). The Michigan model of HRM has emphasized that the different resources are needed to be linked with the organization's objectives. Therefore they must be utilized appropriately and more efficiently. The other models connect the business strategy with the HR model. The various change processes are the essential elements that allow dealing with the different changes, and

Strategic Role of Human Resource Management Policies and Practices in Organizational Change

another critical need that is identified includes another vital factor. It is related to how the change's readiness means how much the organization is ready to accept change. The readiness factor is critical. It is just like a bridge that needs to know about the organization's needs and the activities vital for efficiently and successfully bringing the change.

If additional employees are unwilling to bring the change, it could be quite a hectic process. Employees could also bring the change daily, and this could allow them. The change could be challenging to accept as it provides stress and increases the workload, and such a situation could lead to the employees' resistance. For managing the change successfully, it is argued by the psychology scholars that the vitality and the proactivity both are seen to be playing an important role. Proactive employees are seen to be active participators and take the initiative. It is seen that the organization attains high levels of benefits as they allow managing the organizational change in an efficient way. For bringing the change positively, it is needed that the different organizations first attain satisfaction.

The Human Resource Department (HRD) important role regarding change agents is significant in implementing organizational change. HR practices and policies play a vital role in successful changes in any organization. For maintaining any business in the current competitive marketplace, there is a need to focus on change frequently, and the HR role as a change agent is essential.

A. Ulrich's Four-Role Model

David Ulrich is considered as the HR scholar who proposed many new concepts of contemporary HR practices. In 1996, he proposed the role of HR business partners. The model is given below, and each of the roles is explained in brief.

Figure 1: Ulrich's four-Role Model source: Forbes

The above figure shows four role model sources. The HR business partner is responsible for coordinating all stakeholders (customers) internally and externally. HRBP helps to bring about change, the arrangement of necessary resources, and provision of leadership needed for change, evaluation of initiatives, collaboration with other organizational functions, and implementing any strategic plan in the organization. Human Resources also acts as the change agent to communicate changes in a company concerning expansion, right-sizing, updates about goals & objectives. A change agent is responsible for providing employees opportunities for upskilling their job roles as per required changes in the business through training (internal/external). The change agent virtually supports the organization to adopt the changes for the desired stage of growth or evolution. This administration role within HR is responsible for various types of functions. The administration expert follows changes in country legislation, rules, and regulations, labor or trade laws, or/and occupational health and safety regulations. The administration expert role also focuses on compliance issues; record-keeping so an organization will remain compliant with the laws. Human Resources Department is always responsible for employee welfare, engagement, and protection from any legal or health issue. The employee advocate also leads initiatives to improve employee morale and standards, support the change agent by arranging training and development programs, and ensure there is no discrimination for existing employees regarding promotions and increments to apply for new jobs within the organization.

B. New HR Competency Model

Further research studies helped in understanding the competencies of HR needed for strategic success.

Figure 2: HR Competency Model Source: RBL Group

The above figure 2 shows the competence model source in which HR professionals must have below six competencies to be successful in their profession: Strategic petitioners: HR professional must be business savvy, a good understanding of business stream, expectation of stakeholders and business dynamics, and be able to convert them into talent, culture and leadership actions to achieve the goals. Credible Activists: Building a trusting relationship and a clear understanding of a business's vision and mission are also required key competence of HR professionals. Capability builders: who define, create, and audit

organization skills required for fruitful and sustainable organizations. Change champions: Responsible for initiation and sustain change at all individual, departmental, and institutional levels. HR innovators and integrators: HR Professionals must look for new ways to do HR practices & Policies and integrate this to deliver business solutions. Technology proponents: HR person should be the one who uses technology for efficiency to connect employees and to leverage new communication channels, such as company intranet, email, and social media.

2. Method

A. Nature of Research Study

This research study is a qualitative type, i.e., exploratory research. This research is a case study based research. The researcher has studied the approach of HRM in the XYZ organization. The organization has implemented various changes (small too big). During those change processes, what role HRM has played in ensuring that the people and HRM policies and practices align with the proposed changes, and HR facilitates the change to make it efficient. There are multiples category types of a case study. Yin (1984) has described three essential types: exploratory, descriptive, and explanatory case studies. Exploratory case studies are set to explore any phenomenon in the data, a necessary point of interest for a researcher. Second, descriptive case studies are configured to describe the natural phenomena in the data in question, such as what a reader uses different strategies and how they use them. Lastly, descriptive case studies examine the data closely at a surface and profound level to explain phenomena. This present research is a descriptive case study method as the researcher has used individual cases and described how HR has contributed to successful change management at XYZ Engineering. The data was collected using qualitative accounts as it helped in describing the actual environment and context.

B. Data Collection Sources

Case study evidence can be collected from many sources, like documentation, archival records, interviews, direct observation, participant-observation, and physical artifacts. Each source is associated with an array of data or evidence. (Yin, 2003). The researcher himself is working with the organization and has been an instrumental part of the HR department. The researcher has been involved in the entire process of implemented changes right from the change initiation to implementation. The researcher's own experiences and observations helped identifying HR roles. The other source of data was unstructured interviews. As has already been mentioned, the organization's name and other details have not been disclosed to ensure privacy. Hence unstructured interviews were used just as an additional source of data collection. These interviews involved HR managers. These were more of guided conversations. This informal discussion with other relevant respondents helped the researcher confirm his understanding of the process and functioning. Whatever information has been divulged in this research study is not biased, very transparent, and minimum invasion in the data's privacy and confidentiality has been assured throughout this study.

3. Findings and Discussions

The data was analyzed systematically by tracking down the process of change. The researcher has described the approach of the management in planning and implementing the change. Then stepwise, the processes have been assessed as followed by the organization.

1. GAP Analysis

From a management perspective, this analysis necessitates real performance toward the organization's desired or potential performance. It is mostly applied whenever an organization does deal effectively with the utilization of present resources of an organization, where change is needed, or investment in technology is not producing the potential outcome. It is an essential tool that supports an organization for evaluating and implementing successful change within an organization's workplace, and it is required in a present competitive business environment. It consists of two stages as follows;

A. Creation of Action Plan

In this stage of gap analysis, we should build a clear plan of action to implement change within an organization's workplace. For this, we should look at the main deficiency areas of XYZ Engineering Company and build a firm plan to enhance weak areas of an organization. Following are the essential points for action plan:

- There is a need for an efficient and proper R&D department, with the help of this XYZ Engineering Company, to consider business activities to enhance current procedures or implement change in an organization's workplace.
- There is a need to define transparent HR practices and strategies linked to organizational change within an organization's workplace.
- There is a need to understand and implement HR's role in dynamic changes within an organization's workplace.
- There is a need to identify the core HR practices and strategies critical for significant organizational change within an organization's workplace.
- There is a need to develop an effective communication medium during the implementation of change within an organization's workplace.
- For effective organizational change, HR focuses on employee satisfaction, balanced culture, educational attainment, awareness, and current competition within an organization's workplace.

Figure 3: Gap Analysis Source: www.bersin.com

B. Plan of Action's Backup along with Data & Analysis

In this stage of gap analysis, we must write a report on the main findings using data and analysis. We should correctly join all gap analysis stages. In the end, our key findings, strategic objectives, the standing of an organization in the current situation, their deficiencies, and the implemented change within the organization with overall proper acceptance is stated thoroughly.

2. HR Management Involvement

There is no doubt that supervisors and managers are the two key players in the change initiative. During the time of change, they lead their team, and they can have a positive and negative impact on organizational change within the organization's workplace. In our selected XYZ Engineering Company, the manager is very close to each employee, changing the behavior and processes linked to organizational change. However, it is crucial to handle each step of change and its preparation for managers and supervisors. There are five primary roles performed by management during the time of change within the organization; managers can play the role of coach, advocate, liaison, resistance manager, and communicator (www.Prosci.com, 2017). One research study shows that 84 percent of participants graded the supervisor and manager role in an initiative of change as 'Extremely Important' towards its change.

3. Impact Analysis Process

With the help of impact analysis, we will know the actual management requirements and responsibilities for implementing change within the organization's workplace like in our selected company, i.e., XYZ Engineering Company. There are three most important aspects of this analysis:

- Understand the proper possible deduction for building change within an organization's workplace.
- Rectify all documents, files, theoretical frameworks, and models that might be changed if the entire team comprises the necessary change within an organization's workplace.
- Rectify the tasks for implementing change within an organization's workplace and the estimation of efforts needed to accomplish those desired tasks.

For this research study, the following are the main steps for the impact analysis process towards implementation of change:

1. Identifying the entire sequence where each task regarding change must be executed and how these tasks can be furnished with presently designed functions.
2. Find the implementation of change's critical path, whether a road is suitable for change or not. If change tasks are not on the critical path, then ultimately, the change project-related will also alternate.
3. Judge the effect of aimed change regarding the implementation of change within an organization's workplace.
4. Assess the priority of change through estimating the proportional benefit, cost, penalties, and particular risk equated towards discretionary necessities.
5. Report regarding impact analysis results in entire stakeholders; after this, they can gather information and decide about acceptance and rejection of change within an organization's workplace.

4. Analyzing the Role of HR in Organizational Change

Different impressions arise during the implementation of change within an organization's workplace using HR practices and strategies. The most significant is the cultural impact on organizational change. In a modern active global, local, and regional environment, every firm should be prepared to handle the difficult situation of changes (Suwaryo & Daryanto, 2015).

A. Culture

A culture is several values and beliefs that build norms behavior and prescribe how things get acted. Culture assures us a lot regarding the desired organization. Many experts think it is very tough to change an organization's culture during the implementation of change.

However, it is not real and genuine, and there are some leadership and tactical actions that can build the desired culture. If management is serious regarding implementing change within an organization's workplace, they cannot dismiss an organization's culture. Whenever organizational culture is not coherent towards change that demands consistency, then there is a need to focus and address culture's implementation within an organization's workplace.

Figure 4: Why Culture Matters. Source: www.markumgroup.com

B. Employees Communication

From various research studies, HR managers and senior management have a core role in internal communication towards employees during change within the organization's workplace. Employees must know completely about change and its outcome; without this, the shift cannot be successful for an organization. There is a direct influence of organizational leadership behaviors on various activities within the workplace environment which modify the change, and contributing change demands the utilization of different adjustments of communication techniques for delivering suitable, appropriate, and specific messages and positive feedback, build readiness for implementation of change within the workplace of the organization (Gilley, Gilley, & McMillan, 2009). With weak communication, employees of an organization become negative and uncertain, so each employee cannot see the actual advantage from change; therefore, to resolve this issue, it is needed that HR must develop a robust and efficient communication plan.

C. Employees Motivation

The motivation of employees during the implementation of change within the workplace of an organization by using HR practices and strategies is essential to maintain the entire workforce's morale. The performance

Strategic Role of Human Resource Management Policies and Practices in Organizational Change

and motivation level is the core instrument for implementing change within the organization's workplace and for any organization's success. It spotlights the achievement and evolution of the organization (Dobre, 2013). Following are the main tactics to keep each employee of an organization motivated:

- Communicate regarding change honestly and openly
- Answer each question of employee
- Apply each employee participation and feedback
- Consistently provide training and development programs to employees
- Support each employee to concentrate on targeted goals during organizational change.

Table 1: Employee Motivation Model

	DRIVE	PRIMARY LEVER	ACTIONS
①	Acquire	Reward System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Sharply differentiate good performers from average and poor performers ■ Tie rewards clearly to performance ■ Pay as well as your competitors
②	Bond	Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Foster mutual reliance and friendship among coworkers ■ Value collaboration and teamwork ■ Encourage sharing of best practices
③	Comprehend	Job Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Design jobs that have distinct and important roles in the organization ■ Design jobs that are meaningful and foster a sense of contribution to the organization
④	Defend	Performance-Management and Resource-Allocation Processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Increase the transparency of all processes ■ Emphasize their fairness ■ Build trust by being just and transparent in granting rewards, assignments, and other forms of recognition

Source: Harvard Business Review July-August issue 2008

D. Employees Consultation

During the implementation of change within an organization's workplace, using HR practices and strategies, effective employee consultation, and good communication is very core for successful organizational change, its management performance. There are three central employees meeting are legal aspects:

- Information regarding the economic condition of the organization business
- Discussion and intelligence regarding prospects of employment
- Debate and information regarding significant decisions like an implementation of change within the workplace of an organization.

Figure 5: Consultation for Organizational change Management by John & Cruse (2013)

E. Employees Participation

The organizational change has an effect on each member of the organization inside as well as outside the organization. It is proved that change receivers who felt a high degree of participation tend to have the greater eagerness and change acceptance due to this less stressful situation for implementing change within an organization's workplace. Employee participation demonstrates job autonomy and competencies also nearly associated with service quality perceptions and satisfaction of job, better performance service is because of employee participation. (Azadehdel, Chegini, & Delshad, 2013).

Figure 6: Employee Participation. Source: Vakota & Armenakis (2011)

F. Standardization: Role of ERP

One of the best business management tools is Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), used by the organization as a standardized ERP System to implement change within an organization's workplace. It is a standardized software that facilitates the organization's system concerning integrating applications to manage business processes. It makes all back-office activities automatic related to services, change management, technology, and human resources. Using HR practice and strategies can be implemented within an organization's workplace by applying the change management approach ERP. This method can help differentiate work personalities, education, language, demographics, and skill level. ERP is the practicable instrument that makes productive capacities, capabilities, enhancement of performance, accompaniments towards effective decision-making, and facilities competitive benefits for organization business during organizational change implementation (Ahmed, Zbib, & Arokiasamy, 2006). ERP provides the following resources and training instruments:

- Live Question & Answer
- Live Demos
- Training Workshops
- Eagerness towards assessment
- Free trials
- Walkthroughs

Table 2: Information Drivers for ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) Estimates

Strategic Role of Human Resource Management Policies and Practices in Organizational Change

Source: Grady Brett Beaubouef 2012, <https://gbeaubouef.wordpress.com>

G. Policies Revised

Every policy facilitates outlines and framework principles for organizational change management by using HR practices and strategies to implement change. These policies meditate existing legislation, code of conduct, rules, effective management practice, and ensure a consistent and fair approach towards managing change within an organization's workplace. A Policy revision in an organization builds chaos within a working environment, which provides improvements in operations, creates a better and safer environment for every employee and handles the first reaction of an employee regarding resistance. Following are different stages in the development and revision of policies:

- Firstly, there is a need to found a lack of system according to legislation and organization.
- Next, the development of policy content is driven by the core requirement regarding legislation.
- Then, there is a need to draft the policy regarding the purpose, scope, statement, and responsibilities of an organization towards implementing change within an organization's workplace.
- After that, there is a need to write a complete procedure regarding the step-by-step process and their instructions to accomplish policy.
- Then, there is a need to review policy through the group of concerned managers, leaders, and organization employees.
- Next, if all concerned authorities agree with the policy's aspects, they will formally approve and record their final approval.
- After that, updated copies of this procedure and policies will be distributed among stakeholders, managers, and employees for implementation.
- Finally, there is a need to communicate the changes in policies towards every workforce of the organization.

H. Implementation Stage

It is the final process towards implementation of change within the workplace of an organization by using HR practices, and this can be done through two most famous change management model, i.e., Kotter's Eight-Step Model for change and Lewin's 3-Stage of change.

Kotter's 8 Stages of change model help implement change within the organization's workplace, and success is assured. This approach facilitates a very productive checklist during the change process. On the other hand, Lewin's 3 Steps change process promotes from resistant stage to permanent change. Most of the research recommends this model for the entire organization change process and its success.

Figure 7: Kotter's Eight Steps of change Source: Leading change, John Kotter,2012, Harvard Business Review Press

Figure 8: Lewin's Three Steps of change Source: Lewin K. (1951). Field theory in social science. New York: Harper & Row.

3. Model of the Study

This model consists of five main parts: need for change, communicating the change through different ways, coping up the resistance of tech employees, responding to the need of employees, and final implementation

of change. No doubt that change is needed in the current competitive environment throughout the world; no organization can survive without changing the organization according to their need, because competitors are too much, they are applying comprehensive strategies towards the success of their organization. Therefore, if the organization's management goes through the same procedure demonstrated in the above model during the organizational change, the systematic process for a change will lead the organization towards success in the short-run and long-run.

Figure 9: Model of the Study

In a nutshell, HR has the following most essential roles in managing change, discussed in the study:

- Regular communication during the whole process of change
- Supporting of employees for developing a flexibility
- Demonstrate genuine commitments towards change
- Positive attitude for the change
- Involving of employees for acceptance of change
- Acquiring support from top management for change
- Accurate representation of employee's vision about change
- Reinforcement of change by incentive programs
- Promoting change by using peer and group influence
- Conducting awareness and education about change process to employees
- Handling of resistance to the change from employees

Organizational Change Planning & Start

Figure 10: Change process at XYZ LLC ltd. Source

Figure 11: HR Role in change process at XYZ LLC ltd. Source: Self

4. Conclusion

In this research study, employee satisfaction, effective communication, culture, education level, awareness, and competition are considered independent variables. Moderating variables are HR Practices and Strategies. The core dependent variable of this research variable is organizational change. From in-depth

Strategic Role of Human Resource Management Policies and Practices in Organizational Change

research, we have found that there is direct relationship of independent variables on dependent variable e.g. if employee satisfaction with the help of HR practices and strategies increased then ultimately organizational change will be easy and fruitful. Similarly, if there is sufficient communication is establish then organizational change will also go easy and successful. Also, if balance and maintenance of culture is right then organizational change process will be smooth and successful. And, if education level of employee is high then ultimately they can understand the reason of organizational change quickly and can adopt the new state of change more quickly. Moreover, if awareness program and method towards workforce of organization is good then organizational change will be favorable and have more chances of success. Also, if there is massive competition within corporate departments or external competition among the organization rivals then organizational change and implementation of change within workplace of organization will be active, comfortable and successful.

Therefore, we can say that without effective HR practices and strategies, efficient and successful change within the organization's workplace is impossible. HR plays a vital and fundamental role in changing its present situation towards the new position. It facilitates each element of the organization with proper direction for the successful change process. In other words, HR practices and strategies are the backbones of any organization. During the organizational change process, there is a need to align, integrate and handle each HR practice and procedure towards implementing change within an organization's workplace.

Some of the essential suggestions and recommendations regarding HR practices, strategies and implementation of change within the workplace of an organization, change resistance, technology, customer needs, the economy, growth opportunities, competition, and organizational success are as follows:

Senior management, HR Executives, Leaders, and Managers should understand the firm's present situation; with this, problems can be identified, assign necessary toward each level of the change process, and assessment will be an easy solution to the problem required change. They should pass the vision and need for change to everyone who is participating in the change effort; this will clarify the desired future state of an organization. They should implement change steps orderly because this will help manage and maintain each organizational change level effectively and efficiently. Organizational change should start from the top-level towards the employee because senior management focuses on each issue and new opportunities. The leadership team passes their desires towards the lower level of a workforce with proper support, strength, and direction. The organizational change leader should connect each layer of change, like planning, the definition of strategy, and target settings towards implementation and design of change. Management should build formal face-to-face sessions with an employee of the company. With this different opinion, suggestions, questions, and the right direction regarding the organizational change will arise, and leaders will confidently answer them. The leader should be well communicative towards their workforce because, with effective communication, they can understand the real purpose of change and accept the change quickly. A leader should understand and assess the behaviors and culture at the various organizational change levels, with this readiness toward change. Finally, the leader should prepare for an unexpected situation and speak to each personally, because there is no assurance that each organizational change plan works according to the plan, and by talking to the individual leader can quickly know his/her needs by accomplishing the organization change within the workplace of an organization.

Future studies recommend using the primary data in which the employees and the HR managers should conduct the surveys and the interviews. Moreover, this study could be expanded by comparing the role of change management in different organizations and considering which of them have acceptable HR practices and how they manage the changes. The model proposed at the end of the research study can be applied in similar setups.

REFERENCES

- Adewale, O., & Antbonia, A. (2013). The Impact of Organizational Culture on Human Resource Practices: A Study of Selected Nigerian Private Universities. *Journal of Competitiveness*, 5(4), 115-133. doi:10.7441/joc.2013.04.07
- Ahmed, Z., Zbib, I., & Arokiasamy, S. (2006, July). Resistance To Change And ERP Implementation Success: The Moderating Role of Change Management Initiatives. *Asian Academy of Management Journal*, 11(2), 1-17. Retrieved from <http://web.usm.my/aamj/11.2.2006/aamj%2011-2-1.pdf>
- Alas, R., Allikmae, T., & Varts, R. (2012). Achieving Successful Organizational Change: The Role of Human Resource Management Practices. *E-Leader Manila*.
- Azadehdel, M., Chegini, M., & Delshad, M. (2013). Effective Employee Participation and Organizational Outcomes. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 1(9), 1-7. Retrieved from https://www.arabianjbm.com/pdfs/NG_VOL_1_9/1.pdf
- Azadehdel, M., Chegini, M., & Delshad, M. (2013). Effective Employee Participation and Organizational Outcomes. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 1(9), 1-7. Retrieved from https://www.arabianjbm.com/pdfs/NG_VOL_1_9/1.pdf
- Boselie, P., Dietz, G., & Boon, C. (2005). Commonalities and contradictions in HRM and performance research. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 15, 67-94
- Burma, Z. (2014). Human Resource Management and Its Importance for Today's Organizations. *International Journal of Education and Social Science*, 1(2), 85-94. Retrieved from <http://www.ijessnet.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/9.pdf>
- Chew, M., Cheng, J., & Lazarevic, S. (2006). Managers' Role Implementing Organizational Change: Case of The Restaurant Industry In Melbourne. *Journal of Global Business and Technology*, 2(1), 58-67. Retrieved from http://gbata.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/02/JGBAT_Vol2-1-p6.pdf
- Dobre, O. (2013). Employee Motivation and Organizational Performance. *Review of Applied Socio-Economic Research*, 5(1), 53-60. Retrieved from ftp://ftp.repec.org/opt/ReDIF/RePEc/rse/wpaper/R5_5_DobreOvidiuIlliuta_p53_60.pdf
- Gilley, A., Gilley, J., & McMillan, H. (2009). Organizational Change: Motivation, Communication, and Leadership Effectiveness. *International Society for Performance Improvement*, 21(4), 75-94. Retrieved from http://cstlhcb.semo.edu/hmcmillan/Pubs/Gilley_Gilley_McMillan_2009.pdf
- Iveta, G. (2012). Human Resources Key Performance Indicators. *Journal of Competitiveness*, 4(1), 117-128. doi:10.7441/joc.2012.01.09
- Latta, G. (2009). A Process Model of Organizational Change in Cultural Context (OC3 Model). *Journal of Leadership and Organizational Studies* 16: 19-37

- Liu, Y. (2009). Analysis and Evaluation of Organizational Change Approaches. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 4(12), 234. Retrieved from <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.665.2426&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- Muchira, T., & Kiambati, K. (2015). The Role of Human Resource Development as a Change Agen. *Education Journal*, 4(5), 214-221. Retrieved from <http://article.sciencepublishinggroup.com/pdf/10.11648.j.edu.20150405.15.pdf>
- Manager/Supervisor's Role In Change Management. (2017). Retrieved from Prosci: <https://www.prosci.com/change-management/thought-leadership-library/manager-change-management-role>
- Nitin Nohria, Boris Groysberg, & Linda-Eling Lee. (2008). Employee-Motivation-A-Powerful-New-Model. *Harvard Business Review*, July–August issue. retrieved from <https://Hbr.Org/2008/07/>
- Nutt, C.L. (2003). Academic advising and student retention and persistence –Retrieved November 18, 2008, from the *NACADA Clearinghouse of Academic Advising Resources*
- Sani, D. (2012). Strategic Human Resource Management And Organizational Performance In The Nigerian Insurance Industry: The Impact of Organizational Climate. *Business Intelligence Journal*, 5(1), 8-20. Retrieved from http://www.saycocorporativo.com/saycouk/bij/journal/vol5no1/article_1.pdf
- Suwarjo, J., & Daryanto, H. M. (2015). Organizational Culture Change and its Effect on Change Readiness through Organizational Commitment. *International Journal of Administrative Science & Organization*, 22(1), 68-78. Retrieved from <http://journal.ui.ac.id/index.php/jbb/article/viewFile/5431/3519>
- Tan, C., & Nasurdin, A. (2011). Human Resource Management Practices and Organizational Innovation: Assessing the Mediating Role of Knowledge Management Effectiveness. *Electronic Journal of Knowledge Management*, 9(2), 155-167. Retrieved from <http://www.ejkm.com/issue/download.html?idArticle=289>
- Tummers, L., Kruijen, P. M., Vijverberg, D., & Voesenek, T. (2013). Connecting HRM and change management: How HR practices can stimulate change readiness. EGPA Conference. Paper for the PSG XV: PATI (Public Administration, Technology and Innovation)
- Vakota, C. & Armenakis, A. (2011), Reactions to Organisational Change. A 60-Year Review Of Quantitative Studies. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Sciences*, 47(4), 461-524
- Yin, R. (2009). Case Study Research Design and Methods. 4th ed. Sage, vol.5.
- Yin, R. (1984). Case Study Research Design and Methods. 2nd ed. Sage.